

SITE GPR	YEAR 2010	AREA B	SECTOR	ELEVATION Min: 63.1138 Max: 63.2296	STRATIGRAPHICAL UNIT 1277 <input type="checkbox"/> Natural <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Anthropic	
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In cross-section? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	In elevation drawing? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	Photos: <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No #: 1225, 1226	Photo Model: <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No #:
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DEFINITION Fill for S-most round cut in "Room III"	Covered by <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> SU: 1278	Fills <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> SU: 1278	Filled by <input type="checkbox"/> SU:
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HOW IS LAYER DISTINGUISHED? <input type="checkbox"/> Color <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Composition <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Compaction	FORMATION PROCESS <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Accumulation <input type="checkbox"/> Construction <input type="checkbox"/> Cutting <input type="checkbox"/> Erosion <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse <input type="checkbox"/> Intentional deposition
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INCLUSIONS For each inclusion specify frequency: (f)requent, (m)edium, (r)are			SOIL/MATRIX														
Anthropic	Geological	Organic	clay 10% silt 60% sand 20% <input type="checkbox"/> Granular <input type="checkbox"/> Layered <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Cohesive														
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Pottery M <input type="checkbox"/> Tiles <input type="checkbox"/> Amphorae <input type="checkbox"/> Dolia <input type="checkbox"/> Mosaic tile(s) <input type="checkbox"/> Mortar <input type="checkbox"/> Coins <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Metal (specify) R <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse debris <input type="checkbox"/> Glass <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Nails R <input type="checkbox"/> Marble <input type="checkbox"/> Quarried debris <input type="checkbox"/> Slag <input type="checkbox"/> Brick <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt slabs <input type="checkbox"/> Opus signinum <input type="checkbox"/> Painted plaster <input type="checkbox"/> Burnt Adobe <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify) SF # 226	<input type="checkbox"/> Tufo (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Travertine <input type="checkbox"/> Other Limestone <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Clay } see matrix %'s <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Sand } <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Silt } <input type="checkbox"/> Pebbles (range) <input type="checkbox"/> Gravel (range)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Charcoal R <input type="checkbox"/> Ash <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Animal bones R <input type="checkbox"/> Human bones <input type="checkbox"/> Animal teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Human teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Shells <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)	<table border="1"> <tr> <th>Compaction</th> <th>Color</th> </tr> <tr> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Hard</td> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Black <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Brown</td> </tr> <tr> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Compact</td> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Gray <input type="checkbox"/> Light Brown</td> </tr> <tr> <td><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Friable</td> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Light Gray <input type="checkbox"/> White</td> </tr> <tr> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Loose</td> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Red</td> </tr> <tr> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Soft</td> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Light Yellow</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)</td> </tr> </table>	Compaction	Color	<input type="checkbox"/> Hard	<input type="checkbox"/> Black <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Brown	<input type="checkbox"/> Compact	<input type="checkbox"/> Gray <input type="checkbox"/> Light Brown	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Friable	<input type="checkbox"/> Light Gray <input type="checkbox"/> White	<input type="checkbox"/> Loose	<input type="checkbox"/> Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Red	<input type="checkbox"/> Soft	<input type="checkbox"/> Light Yellow		<input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)
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UNIT LIMITS (also indicate on overlay)	Depth: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original
Northern Limit <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit	
Southern Limit <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit	
Western Limit <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit	
Eastern Limit <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit	

STRATIGRAPHICAL SEQUENCE	
Is equal to:	Is bound to (only for masonry):
Is abutted by:	Abuts:
Is covered by: 1278	Covers:
Is cut by:	Cuts:
Is filled by:	Fills: 1278

OBSERVATIONS Small Find 226 (metal wall-hook). Went deeper than the hole to the N. I excavated with a trowel on Wed (28-7-10), which was sunny & dry.

DESCRIPTION
Position within sector: SW corner of "Room III"
Shape: ovalar

For layers complete this section:
Surface (slope direction; visible inclusions): sloped down S-wards on surface
Observations about inclusions (Clusters? Deposition slope) A lot of rocks (larger than cobbles clustered e bottom)
Observations about thickness (Increases? Decreases?): in middle, cut goes all the way to bedrock, but near sides, slopes
Nature of the interface with layer below: sharp diffuse commingled other (specify)

<p>For cuts complete this section:</p> <p>Cut edges: <input type="checkbox"/> rounded <input type="checkbox"/> straight</p> <p>Cut sides <input type="checkbox"/> straight <input type="checkbox"/> concave <input type="checkbox"/> convex <input type="checkbox"/> sloping</p> <p>Cut bottom: <input type="checkbox"/> flat <input type="checkbox"/> concave <input type="checkbox"/> irregular</p> <p>How is cut top edge? <input type="checkbox"/> sharp <input type="checkbox"/> rounded</p> <p>How is cut bottom edge? <input type="checkbox"/> sharp <input type="checkbox"/> rounded</p> <p>Observations:</p>	<p>Sketch for layers and/or cuts (indicate North):</p>
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For structural remains complete this section

Alignment:

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify)

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

Concrete inclusions:

Material Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)
 Size Small (range) _____ Medium (range) _____ Large (range) _____ Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cmz

Wall Facing:

Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)

Complete this section for foundations Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

floor/revetment type

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus Sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify)

Wall finishing Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains:

Description:

Sketch (if applicable, indicate North)

INTERPRETATION

Fill of a fairly round truncation, maybe a posthole or a robbing activity?

SOIL SAMPLING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets): *N/A*

Sample quantity (buckets): *2*

Sample fraction (%):

NON SOIL SAMPLES: Yes No

If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.):

Size:

SIEVING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY

Good Fair Poor

Filled-out by *CAK* on *28.07.2010*

Revised by *CHM* on *28.07.2010*

PDFd by *JSM* on *30.07.2010*

Entered by _____ on _____